

SYNTHESES OF N¹-HETEROCYCLIC SULPHANILAMIDES

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A few sulphanilamides containing chromone derivatives as a substituent at N¹ position have been synthesised and tested for their antibacterial properties.

The N¹-heterocyclic derivatives of sulphanilamides are the important group of sulphanilamides, which show increased bacteriostatic potencies and better therapeutic response in clinical trials. The major sulpha drugs, e.g. sulphapyridine, sulphadiazine, etc. are the members of this series. The heterocyclic substituents at N¹ position, which have been found effective so far, appear to be pyridyl, pyrimidyl, thiazolyl and guanidyl. The present communication deals with the syntheses of sulphanilamides or their derivatives having chromone derivatives as substituents at N¹.

When the aminochromones, obtained by the reduction of nitrochromones (cf. this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 59), were condensed with *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride in the presence of pyridine, the acetylsulphanilamides were formed. These derivatives on acid hydrolysis yielded the corresponding sulphanilamides. In general, the preparations of sulphanilamidochromones exhibited several difficulties and very poor yields were obtained at final stages. In a few cases, free sulphanilamides could not be obtained from their acetyl derivatives.

Aminochromones, acetylsulphanilamides, and free sulphanilamides obtained in this work were tested against *M. Tuberculosis*. These do not appear to possess appreciable activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

(I). *5-Sulphanilamido-6-methoxychromone* ($R_1 = \text{NH}_2\text{SO}_2\text{NH}$; $R_2 = \text{OMe}$; $R_3 = R_4 = \text{H}$).—A suspension of 5-nitrochromone (4 g.) in 5% HCl (100 c.c.) was heated on a water bath to 80° and granulated tin (5 g.) was added to it in small lots. After heating for 4 hrs. the reaction mixture was filtered hot, and the filtrate was diluted to 500 c.c. Tin was removed by H₂S and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure till the hydrochloride of the amine began to separate. The residual liquid was taken in ethanol, and dry ether was added to the solution to precipitate the hydrochloride of 5-amino-6-methoxychromone, yield 2.4 g. For purification it was dissolved in ethanol and reprecipitated by ether, when crystalline cubes were obtained, m.p. 195-200°. (Found: N, 6.4; equiv., 227.5. C₁₀H₁₀O₃NCl requires N, 6.11%; equiv., 231).

The above hydrochloride (1 g.) was suspended in dry pyridine (5 c.c.), and acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride (1.2 g.) was added to the above suspension. The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath for 2 to 3 hrs. The contents of the flask turned blackish violet. The coloured solution was poured in dilute HCl, when 5-acetylsulphanilamido-6-methoxychromone separated as a crystalline solid. The solid was collected and crystallised from ethanol in small needles, m.p. 240-42° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.5. C₁₉H₁₈O₄N₂S requires N, 7.2%).

The above methoxychromone (0.7 g.) was suspended in HCl (10 c.c., 10%) and the mixture was refluxed on a sand bath for 3 hrs., when the total substance went into solution. The acidic solution was cooled and neutralised by sodium carbonate, when a yellowish crystalline solid separated.

The 5-sulphanilamido-6-methoxychromone, thus obtained, was filtered, washed, dried, and crystallised from benzene in yellowish prisms, m.p. 202-203°. (Found: N, 7.7. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 8.0%).

(II). 8-Sulphanilamido-7-methoxychromone ($R_1=R_2=H$; $R_3=OMe$; $R_4=NH_2SO_2NH$).—The suspension of 8-nitro-7-methoxychromone (1 g.) in acetic acid (5 c.c., 10%) was heated on a water bath, and powdered reduced iron (1 g.) was added to the suspension in small lots with vigorous stirring. After the addition was over, it was heated further for half an hour, and filtered hot. The filtrate was neutralised with $NaHCO_3$ and extracted with benzene. The extract was dried over sodium sulphate, filtered, and the solvent removed. 8-Amino-7-methoxychromone, thus obtained, was crystallised from benzene in yellow needles, m.p. 108-109°. (Found: N, 6.3. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 6.0%).

A mixture of 8-amino-7-methoxychromone (1 g.), dry pyridine (5 c.c.) and acetylaminosulphonyl chloride (1.2 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 110-20° for 3 hrs. The mixture was cooled and added to dilute HCl, when 8-acetylsulphanilamido-7-methoxychromone separated as a solid. It was crystallised from ethanol as yellow plates, m.p. 250-51°. (Found: N, 7.3. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6N_2S$ requires N, 7.2%).

The above acetylsulphanilamide was hydrolysed by 10% HCl as described under (I). On neutralisation of the acidic solution, (II) was obtained as a solid, which was crystallised from benzene in fine needles, m.p. 230-40°. (Found: N, 7.8. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 8.0%).

(III). 6-Acetylsulphanilamidochromone ($R_1=H$; $R_2=CH_3CO.NH.SO_2NH$; $R_3=R_4=H$).—6-Nitrochromone (1 g.) was reduced by iron and acetic acid as described under 8-amino-7-methoxychromone when 6-aminochromone was obtained, yield 0.25 g. It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 210-11°. (Found: N, 8.9. $C_9H_7O_2N$ requires N, 8.6%).

On condensing acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride (1.3 g.) with 6-aminochromone (1 g.) in presence of pyridine (5 c.c.) at 110-20°, (III) was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 216°. (Found: 7.6. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5N_2S$ requires N, 7.8%).

The hydrolysis of the chromone with (i) 10% HCl, (ii) 10% ethanol and (iii) sodium methoxide at 30° did not meet with success.

(IV). 8-Sulphanilamido-5-methoxychromone ($R_1=OMe$; $R_2=R_3=H$; $R_4=NH_2SO_2NH$).—8-Nitrochromone (5 g.) was reduced by tin (10 g.) and HCl (200 c.c., 10%) at 90° according to the usual procedure. After 2 hours the hot reaction mixture was filtered and diluted with water. It was treated with H_2S to remove tin, and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure till the hydrochloride appeared as a reddish precipitate. It was dissolved in minimum quantity of absolute ethanol, and the hydrochloride was precipitated by the addition of dry ether as a reddish yellow solid, m.p. 200-10° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.1. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5N_2Cl$ requires N, 6.11%). The hydrochloride was found to be unstable on exposure.

An attempt was made to obtain the aminochromone by dissolving the hydrochloride in minimum quantity of water and extracting the amine with chloroform after making ~~it~~ alkaline with ammonia. On removal of chloroform it was obtained as a liquid which decomposed spontaneously. The liquid aminochromone, when treated with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, yielded 8-acetamino-5-methoxychromone. It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 210-12°. (Found: N, 6.08. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 6.0%).

Attempt to prepare 8-sulphanilamido-5-methoxychromone from the above hydrochloride or amine did not meet with success.